

Play and Games in Antiquity: Definition, Transmission, Reception
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Abstracts

Francesca Berti, Tübingen

Meanings of Tradition in the Context of Play

This paper investigates what we mean by traditional games and how they are transmitted. When referring to past practices of play, whether those of recent or ancient times, we often refer to them as “traditional games”. Yet, to say that a game is “traditional” does not refer to any precise category, as is, for example, the category of “board games”; neither does it represent any clear dichotomy, such as in the distinction between analogical and digital games; further still, it does not necessarily refer to any particular moment in time as there is no separation between past and present, since we usually talk of “traditional games” to refer to games that are still played nowadays. Indeed, the adjective “traditional” might appear functional to distinguishing some kinds of games from others, but it only seems to suggest a rather nebulous quality. The paper suggests that in several traditional games, before being part of the tradition of a community and its territory, the quality of being traditional is borne by the experience of playing the game itself, by the repetition of its set of rules, and by the transmission of its objects of play. These are the sorts of games that form traditions: sometimes, a game remains peculiar to a specific territory, sometimes “it travels” (Schädler 2003), giving rise to the creation of a new tradition.

Simone Beta, Sienna

Studiare la lingua e la letteratura greca divertendosi: gli indovinelli greci nelle scuole di Bisanzio / Étudier la langue et la littérature en s’amusant: les devinettes grecques dans les écoles de Byzance

Nel celebre manoscritto dell’Antologia Palatina, una ricchissima collezione di epigrammi greci compilata a Costantinopoli nel decimo secolo d.C., il quattordicesimo libro, che contiene enigmi, oracoli e problemi matematici, è preceduto da una breve prefazione dove si legge che questi componimenti singolari sono stati raccolti con l’intenzione di far ‘esercitare’ (γυμνασίας χάριν, *gymnasias charin*) lo spirito degli studenti ‘che amano la fatica’ (φιλόπονοι, *philoponoi*).

Molti epigrammi enigmatici sembrano infatti essere stati scritti per insegnare ai giovani studenti di Costantinopoli alcune materie come la grammatica, la letteratura e la mitologia attraverso un metodo basato principalmente sul gioco. Del resto, l’utilizzo pedagogico di simili forme para-letterarie per stimolare l’apprendimento è attestato non solo dal particolare spirito agonistico che era comune ai Greci, ma anche da alcune testimonianze tarde che parlano esplicitamente dell’uso dei *griphoi* (un sinonimo di *ainigmata* ‘enigmi’) nelle aule scolastiche bizantine.

La relazione presenterà alcuni epigrammi del quattordicesimo dell’Antologia Palatina, insieme ad altri componimenti analoghi ancora inediti, per fornire un quadro sintetico di questo particolare genere poetico ancora poco conosciuto.

Chiara Bianchi, Milano

“Alexandrian Counters”: Finds in Archaeological Contexts

The so called “Alexandrian counters” are discoid in shape and are made either of bone or ivory; on the obverse side various scenes are found whereas on the reverse numerals in Latin and Greek (from 1 to 15) are present; sometimes in the middle an inscription, in Greek, identifies the scene. Initially they were thought to be theatre tickets but the discovery of an infant burial from Kerch (Pantikapeion) containing a complete series of counters, numbered from 1 to 15, changed the latter theory and they are now considered gaming pieces.

They were considered to be of Alexandrian origin because the scenes engraved often represented monuments, places of cult or landscapes connected to Alexandria and the Nile delta. Actually many other images were found: gods from the Graeco-Roman and Egyptian pantheon, portraits of Roman Emperors from the Julio-Claudian dynasty, heroes, poets, athletes, caricatures, theatrical masks, victory wreaths, animals, plants and inanimate objects... These counters can be dated between around the Caesarian period to the end of the Julio-Claudian dynasty with Nero, even though some pieces continued to be used for quite a while.

They have been discovered throughout the Roman world: along the coasts of the eastern Mediterranean, along the northern shores of the Black Sea, in Greece, in Italy and as far away off as central Europe. We do not really know how the game was played; it is not mentioned in ancient sources and all interpretations are up to questioning.

This paper will consider again the “Alexandrian counters”: it is difficult to understand how they were used, but it is possible to analyze better the contexts where they were found. There are many items of unknown provenance, but there are also some finds from graves or settlements that can give many useful information. A map of distribution of these findings will be presented with some preliminary data, in order to offer a new contribution to the discussion.

Anton Bierl, Basel

Choral Dance as a Play: *paizein* in Greek Drama

Paizein ('to play') is one of the *termini technici* for dancing in Greek culture. This paper will explore the anthropological implications of this interesting fact. After a glance on Plato's explanations we will investigate how this notion stands in accordance and in contrast to the poetics of Greek tragedy and in what way it is more appropriate for comedy and satyr-play. The exuberance of playing children (*paides*) expresses the gay happiness of the comic atmosphere and the activities of the satyrs who, to some extent, seem to be reprojected to their status as children. We will demonstrate this on a selection of texts, esp. *Frogs* and *Cyclops*.

Barbara Carè, Athens

Appropriating the Past: New Perspectives on Game Studies. The Ancient and Modern Game of Astragals

The paper explores forms of continuity between past and present games and discusses the crucial question about how we can deal with such dynamic and polyvocal kind of evidence in our attempt to reconstruct the past. A particular focus will be given to the game played with *astragali*, survived over centuries and spread around the world. Modern forms of entertainment involving these bones will be examined in the historical framework of Greek and Roman games.

Salvatore Costanza, Fribourg

Pollux témoin des jeux : continuité, survie et réception dans la culture ludique néogrecque

Le lexicographe du II^e siècle de notre ère Pollux est évidemment un témoin privilégié de la culture ludique grecque ancienne, dont il décrit plusieurs rites et pratiques dans son dictionnaire classé de façon thématique, l'*Onomasticon*. Ces jeux ont une fonction de cohésion sociale à travers la définition des rôles assignés aux enfants, garçons et filles, en tant que futurs citoyens et mères de citoyens. Les documents néogrecs du XIX^e-XX^e siècle confirment cette fonction attribuée aux passetemps des enfants. Ma contribution vise à mettre en évidence la continuité et la survie des jeux décrits par Pollux dans la pratique ludique de la Grèce contemporaine. Des parallèles tirés du folklore néogrec sont relatifs à la formation et à l'instruction des jeunes filles et garçons lors du passage de l'enfance à la maturité, ce qui équivaut souvent à la transition matrimoniale. La comparaison entre l'expérience ancienne et moderne se révèle très instructive. Nous examinerons dans cette perspective des jeux tels que la « Petite Hélène » (Ἡ μικρὴ Ἑλένη), « Où vas-tu, Mme Marie? » (Ποῦ θὰ πᾶς κυρά Μαρία;) « Pétrin » (Πινακωτή), et d'autres encore. Nous pourrions ainsi évaluer les modes de transmission et de réélaboration du patrimoine ludique grec ancien au cours des siècles.

Charles Doyen, Louvain

Osselets ou poids ?

De nombreux astragales en os, en pierre ou en métal (plomb, bronze, argent, or) furent découverts en contexte archéologique ou circulent sur le marché des antiquités. Dans la plupart des cas, il est difficile de faire la distinction entre les astragales anatomiques, les astragales effectivement utilisés dans un cadre ludique, les astragales représentant des jouets qui servent d'offrandes dans les tombes ou les sanctuaires, et les astragales qui n'ont pas de rapport direct avec le monde du jeu. À cette dernière catégorie appartient à coup sûr un intéressant corpus de poids en bronze en forme d'astragales, pesant de quelques grammes à plusieurs dizaines de kilogrammes, qui furent produits sur la côte syro-levantine, en Asie Mineure et en Grèce, de l'époque archaïque à l'époque impériale. L'astragale est également utilisé comme symbole pondéral, en particulier à Athènes, où il sert à identifier le statère (στατήρ), « peseur » par excellence et unité centrale du système pondéral. En étudiant l'astragale comme poids et comme symbole pondéral, nous souhaitons contribuer à l'étude de cet objet polysémique et jeter un regard nouveau sur le développement du jeu des osselets en Grèce ancienne, qui valut notamment à Patrocle d'être exilé de la maison de son père à la suite du meurtre de son partenaire (Il., XXIII, 85–88).

Julien du Bouchet, Montpellier

Jouer en rêve : autour d'Artémidore

Le rêve peut mettre en scène un jeu, et, de fait, visant à donner une impression d'exhaustivité dans son recueil de thèmes oniriques, Artémidore ne manque pas d'évoquer quelques jeux, de diverses natures. On tentera, à travers l'analyse des passages concernés et de quelques autres, d'évaluer l'apport de l'onirocritique à la connaissance des jeux dans l'Antiquité.

Regine Fellmann, Kantonsarchäologie Aargau, Brugg

Games and Toys from the Legionary Camp of Vindonissa – an Overview

The paper will give an overview on games and toys coming from excavations in Vindonissa (Windisch, Kanton Aargau, CH). During the last 10 years, large parts of the civil settlement around the legionary fortress, the *canabae*

legionis, have been excavated. A special focus will therefore lie on game counters and their spatial distribution in this military / civilian context.

Michel Fuchs, Lausanne

Jeux d'Eros et jeux d'enfants : la corde, le dé et l'osselet en messagers du temps

La reprise des quelques scènes connues sur mosaïque ou peinture murale montrant des Amours, des enfants ou des jeunes gens en train de jouer à l'aide d'une corde, de dés ou d'osselets invite à s'interroger sur la signification des scènes choisies. Partant de la description attentive et de la détermination des jeux représentés, leur étude conduit à les intégrer à une représentation du temps, suspendu ou éternel, que ce soit dans la vision pompéienne de Médée et de ses enfants ou sur la scène de la Via Portuense à Rome en passant par les Amours de la Maison des Cerfs à Herculaneum.

Mark Golden, Winnipeg

Play, Dance, Sport, War: Ancient Greek Bodies in Motion

Famous passages of Greek literature build on contrasts between play and sport (Homer, *Iliad* 23.85-88) or dance and sport (Herodotus 6.126-129). But such categories tend to become less clear-cut on further examination. Our own assumptions pose problems: most of our sports use a ball, an emblem of childhood play for the Greeks. More important is the fact that play, sport and dance shared similarities for the Greeks at the same time as they demonstrated differences. For example, *paizein*, 'to play', refers to dancing as early as Homer, and teams of dancers figured in competitive festivals: dance was the team sport of the Greeks. As Peter Wilson puts it, dance was part of a 'spectrum of collective activities that leads, at one extreme, to war'. What can we learn from the places where the Greeks marked distinctions on this spectrum?

Cleo Gougouli, Patras

The Search for Cultural Continuities in Studies of Modern Greek Play and Games: Some Theoretical and Methodological Questions

The study of play, games and toys in Modern Greece has been characterized for many years by a classicist approach expressed in terms of a doctrine of cultural continuity between Ancient and Modern Greek culture, which was formed in the context of particular political and ideological developments that led to the establishment of the Modern Greek Nation state in 1830. Any discussion on transmission, continuity and change regarding play, games and toys should therefore take into account not only the methodological issues concerning the Ancient Greek material but also the particular biases of the majority of sources on "traditional" forms of play and plaything from the 19th century to the present.

Drawing on performance theory and recent theoretical developments in material culture studies the paper will discuss some methodological questions arising from the study of a broad range of literature on "traditional" games, play and toys in Modern Greece.

Miguel Herrero de Jáuregui, Madrid

Early Christian Attitudes to Child Playing

The references to child playing and games in the Christian writings of the first centuries are not numerous and almost always take an apologetic binary approach: along the anthropological axis, natural childish innocence vs. adult corruption; in pedagogical models, education vs. perversion; from an orthodoxy-focused perspective, religion vs. superstition. In metaphors built with images of child playing, in literature of advice for child upbringing, and in the descriptions of toys and playing scenes, there is always a thin but firm line between praiseworthy simplicity and destructive puerility that is projected with remarkable continuity in different authors and contexts. Departing from one of the most influential Christian apologetic works, Clement of Alexandria's *Protrepticus*, in which all these attitudes can be observed, this paper will review the most relevant passages in early Christian literature, in which only one heterodox text, the so-called Infancy Gospel of Thomas, stands strikingly out from the aforementioned dichotomies.

Andromache Karanika, Irvine

Midas and the "Pot" Game: Intertextual Insights into an Ancient Game

One of the most popular circular games in antiquity seems to be the so-called "Pot" game (*chytra*) which enacts a dialogue between one child wearing the 'pot' who takes the persona of "Midas," and others about to kick him and play the role of the pot-wearing "Midas." Pollux's *Onomasticon* (9.114) transmits the poetics of this game which, similar with other circular children's games, present a rudimentary yet cryptic dialogue between the players as they rotate their roles. This paper illuminates a complex intertextual relation with comedy. By following two different threads, the presence of Midas in Greek myth and lore and also the comic stage, and the persistent use of pots as theatrical props creating slapstick humor and laughter in several comic moments from both extant comedies (e.g.,

Ar. *Thesm.* 403, 505; *Lys.* 315; *Av.* 365) and fragments (Crates, Epicharmus and Timocles) this paper seeks to explore a fascinating dialogue around the common themes between children's and adults' genres of performance. Furthermore, it seeks to delve into questions of not only generic interactions but also ritual and gender inversions and ideologies of *othering* individuals and groups of individuals in a seemingly playful tone. Ultimately, such rhymes both mirror and undermine adult performative modes.

Nikolina Kei, Paris

Dessins et jeux fictifs

La communication sera consacrée à deux dessins repris dans diverses publications sur le jeu antique dont celle de L. Deubner, « Spiele und Spielzeug der Griechen » (*Die Antike*, 6, 1930). Les dessins reproduisent les images qui ornent deux vases, un canthare attique et un petit cratère italiote. Le premier représente une fille tenant un objet faussement identifié comme un cerf-volant, le second un enfant sur un cheval bâton. Représentations uniques et pour cela très intrigantes pour les spécialistes du jeu, elles sont malheureusement publiées sans que leur support (type de vase), leur origine, leur lieu de découverte et leur lieu de conservation soient cités. Utilisés en tant que simples illustrations, ces deux dessins seront l'occasion de nous interroger sur des questions d'historiographie, de sources et de méthodes.

Stephen Kidd, Brown University

Is Play an Emotion? An Inquiry into Greek *Paidia*

Paidia, the ancient Greek word for “play”, was conceived to be something much closer to an emotion than its modern European equivalents allow. It is not an activity that is engaged in “for pleasure”, as if by partaking in certain activities called “play”, for example, rolling dice or jumping rope, a player might trigger some sort of pleasure reward. *Paidia* is rather a feeling of pleasure that spills over into the physical manifestations of that pleasurable feeling. Just as an emotion like fear might cause someone to flail their arms frantically and run screaming in a certain direction, *paidia* causes someone, in a perceived overflow of pleasurable feeling, to dance, sing, and make certain movements just for the pleasure of it. In the case of fear, the physical manifestation of that feeling is regularly denoted by the verb *phobeomai*: one is being “routed” and so running away. In the case of *paidia*, the physical manifestation is denoted by the verb *paizo* which regularly covers singing and dancing as well as more typical forms of English play like rolling dice, playing ball games, and play-fighting.

Christian Laes, Antwerp

***Ludus* and Education**

The question of play at ancient schools can only be solved by a diversified approach that carefully distinguishes the different layers of the problem. First, we need to ask whether the apparent semantic link between school and leisure which exists in both Latin and Greek ever brought the ancient writers to explicit acknowledgments of the relation between the two, or on the contrary of the fundamental contradictions between both concepts. Second, it is worth looking at statements about the intrinsic value of play for the educational process, and to see whether such valuations were ever linked to schools and education in the classroom. Third, I scrutinise the fragments that possibly point to play and recreation or the absence of it in schools. In the conclusion, I fully take into account the broader context of schools in Antiquity to come to a nuanced answer regarding the question.

Michel Manson, Toulouse

Un érudit inattendu : Louis Becq de Fouquières, le premier historien des jeux et jouets de l'Antiquité

Anatole France a dit de Louis Becq de Fouquières qu'il était l'homme d'un seul livre. Il désignait ainsi les éditions critiques de l'œuvre d'André Chénier que Louis Becq de Fouquières a publié de 1862 à 1881, éditant aussi des poèmes de Ronsard, Du Bellay, Baïf, Malherbe et les œuvres de de Pange, ami d'André Chénier. Ajoutons qu'il est l'auteur de traités de versification, de prosodie, de diction et de lecture à haute voix, et qu'il a ouvert la voie à la mise en scène théâtrale moderne par son traité de 1884. Comment ce critique littéraire, ce théoricien de la poésie a-t-il pu écrire un livre sur Les Jeux des Anciens (1869), un autre sur Aspasia de Milet (1872) où il fait montre d'une érudition en grec et en latin, avec une connaissance étonnante, non seulement des littératures antiques, mais aussi des découvertes archéologiques et des objets. Lui qui n'était pas universitaire, mais homme de lettres, comment a-t-il pu se former au point de devenir l'un des « savants » antiquisant du Second Empire ? Nous chercherons à répondre à cette question en évoquant sa biographie et en étudiant ses références et ses concepts sur l'Antiquité et sur les Jeux.

Katarzyna Marciniak, Warsaw (*ERC Our Mythical Childhood*)

Du Rubicon à la chambre d'enfants ou à la réception de l'expression *Alea iacta est* dans la culture des jeunes.

En franchissant le Rubicon, César n'a pas seulement changé le destin de la République Romaine, mais aussi celui de toute la culture populaire qui allait naître. Après deux mille ans, l'image de César au bord du Rubicon est

iconique. Encore plus iconiques sont les paroles qu'il aurait dit: *Alea iacta est*. C'est un paradoxe (pas le seul dans l'histoire de la réception de l'Antiquité), qu'une partie du code de notre culture provient au fait des mots jamais articulés sous cette forme – d'une version latine des mots de César qui les a prononcés en grec et à l'impératif. La vérité historique (nomen omen dans le contexte de la conférence) joue cependant un rôle secondaire. Ce qui compte, c'est l'utilisation faite par les époques suivantes de l'héritage de l'Antiquité pour exprimer leurs propres pensées et idées. Grâce à cela, la réception devient un miroir à travers lequel nous pouvons apprendre à connaître mieux ces époques et nous-mêmes, aussi aujourd'hui. Mais sera-t-il toujours comme ça, quand les effets des changements sous le slogan „à bas le latin” commencent à se manifester de plus en plus fortement?

Cette présentation se concentre sur la réception apparemment la plus éloignée de César en termes de temps et de contenu. Je montrerai le fonctionnement de l'expression *Alea iacta est* aux XX^e et XXI^e siècles dans la culture pour les jeunes. Je vais essayer de saisir le phénomène de la signification de ces mots dans des circonstances moins favorables: après la diminution du latin dans l'éducation, qui semble couper les nouvelles générations de l'ancienne référence. En analysant des exemples de différentes sphères linguistiques (anglais, allemand, français et polonais), créés par des adultes – je voudrais montrer comment notre jeu avec l'Antiquité continue aujourd'hui et à quel bord du Rubicon nous nous trouvons.

Barbara Pfäffli, Augusta Raurica

Games of a Town

Augusta Raurica was a Roman colony town founded in the territory of the Celtic tribe of the Raurici. In its heyday in the 2nd century AD some 15'000 people lived here. A rather large part of the ancient town area has been excavated and approximately 1.6 million finds recovered. I will try to give an overview of the finds related to play and games and then present some enigmatic objects that may or may not be connected to the theme.

Clare Rowan, Warwick (*ERC Token Communities in the Ancient Mediterranean*)

Sorting Fun from Fiction : Were “*tesserae*” Gaming Pieces?

The Latin word “*tesserae*” has become a catch all in modern scholarship, used to describe a variety of paranumismatic objects that were made of different materials, carried wildly differing designs, and which served different functions. This paper sets out to clarify possible purposes of different types of “*tesserae*”, part of research being conducted in the ERC-funded project *Token Communities in the Ancient Mediterranean*. Archaeological finds strongly support the idea that some bone or ivory “*tesserae*” functioned as gaming pieces, but a broader perspective of “*tesserae*” reveals that this was not the case for all bone counters from antiquity, nor “*tesserae*” in general. Examining a broad array of “*tesserae*” from across the ancient Mediterranean, it is evident that tokens of different materials were used in different locations for different purposes. Presenting previously unpublished material from museums, this paper will identify specimens which may have been used as gaming pieces and will question the idea that “*spintriae*” (bronze tokens carrying numbers) and their counterparts were used in games. “*Spintriae*” have, in the absence of other suggestions, been interpreted as counters used in a game now lost to us. However, their imagery is also found on lead pieces that may be connected to the celebration of festivals, suggesting an alternative use for the bronze pieces. A festival context, similar to gaming, also invited the use of images of a celebratory or joyful nature. Even if many “*tesserae*” were not directly used in games, they attest to the atmosphere in which games and Roman celebrations occurred.

Victoria Sabetai, Athens

Playing at the Festival: *Aiora*, a Swinging Ritual

A small number of disparate literary sources and vase-paintings inform us about a custom that took place in ancient Athens and concerned swinging in the framework of a festival (*Aiora*). Although swinging could be practiced at any time and by anybody, the designation of a particular day for its collective performance by various segments of society ascribes to it a ritual character. The incorporation of an otherwise secular ludic activity in the context of a religious festivity highlights the potential of games to function also as rituals able to convey cultural ideals and expectations due to their performative character.

This paper traces the history of scholarship on the *Aiora* with special emphasis on the visual evidence, which, by contrast to the much later testimonia, is the only evidence that dates to the 6th and 5th centuries BC. Frequent questions previously asked by scholars of religion have focused on which festival was the one during which ritual swinging was performed and at what exact time within the sequence of cultic events it took place. The visual evidence furnishes interesting details regarding the protagonists of the swinging ritual and sheds light on the construction of gender in the Greek world. It also documents the swinging ritual's early manifestation on the religious and cultic level.

Karin Schlapbach, Fribourg

Ludus as Dance and Bodily Movement

This paper addresses the physical dimension of play and games by examining one of the common words for dancing in Latin, ludere. The link between ludus and dance is arguably even stronger than that between the Greek paizein and dancing. This raises interesting questions as to the place of play and dance in Roman culture, which is often portrayed as less ludic and fun-loving than its Greek neighbour.

The paper will discuss a representative sample of dancing scenes in Latin literature that feature the vocabulary of ludus, and it will explore in particular the association between playing, mimesis, and collective and coordinated movement (i.e., choral dance).

Renzo Tosi, Bologna

Pollux et les noms des jeux

Although the onomastic way of ranging materials is very ancient, the Pollux' is the only one survived Greek work whose structure is onomastic. This way was the most common one until late Alexandrian age and it was probably the ranging way in Aristophanes of Byzantium's works. Furthermore, Onomastica of Eratosthenes are source of Pollux. The ranging way is 'horizontal', the criteria are semantic fields and lexical links, usually it is not possible to distinguish between lemmata and interpretamenta. In reality, the text of Pollux that arrived to us is deeply abridged. Therefore, it is probable that genuine Pollux had a lot of explications and quotations of classical texts that were cut. As regards to sources, it is important to remind that Pollux wrote in Commodus' age, inside of a controversy about the correct usage of Greek language. His attitude was 'Atticistic', but in his opinion many authors could be imitated. In my opinion, this not closely limited canon caused his polemic against Phrynichus, as it is possible to see above all in last book of the Onomasticon. It is necessary to know these general characteristics of the work analysing two sections about plays (9,96-106 and 3,140-145). It is noteworthy to notice that sometimes in the horizontal structure there are interferences of scholiastic elements. It is impossible to understand whether such situations are original or due to the cuts of the text. It is also very difficult to understand its stylistic characteristics when Pollux is the only one source of a term.

Marco Vespa, Fribourg

L'origine du jeu : récits grecs sur l'invention des pratiques ludiques entre Palamède, Prométhée et Theuth

Si les pratiques ludiques sont à considérer comme des produits culturels à part entière qui structurent la vie sociale des sociétés avec la même importance que l'écriture, le droit ou encore la politique, ces pratiques néanmoins acquièrent très souvent le statut d'objet 'naturel' depuis toujours présent dans la vie sociale et dont l'origine n'est pas à rechercher dans un moment précis ou dans une figure historique particulière.

L'Antiquité grecque a cependant réfléchi sur les origines du jeu en nous livrant plusieurs récits qui lient l'invention des dés ou du ballon à d'endroits géographiques divers et à de protagonistes différents de région à région de la Lydie à l'Égypte en passant par la Grèce.

Cette brève intervention cherchera à dresser une comparaison critique entre ces traditions narrativement diverses en se concentrant sur la mise en discours de chaque récit dans le but de mettre en lumière les catégories mobilisées et les objectifs énonciatifs des textes considérés.

Arnaud Zucker, Nice

Les proverbes relatifs aux jeux, chez Pollux et les parémiographes

Les jeux se prêtent bien à une fixation formulaire et à un traitement lexicographique, car ils sont l'occasion de formules codées, et de nombreux jeux sont même désignés par une formule, en Grèce comme ailleurs (« un, deux, trois, soleil » « qui perd gagne », « la balle au prisonnier », « ni oui, ni non », « je te tiens par la barbichette », « accroche-décroche », etc.). Les recueils parémiographiques transmettent une douzaine de ces expressions proverbiales et, comme les traités de type lexicographique de Pollux (ou de Suétone), ils proposent pour justifier ces usages des motivations qui peuvent nous éclairer sur les modalités de certains de ces jeux, ou des détails de leur déroulement. Mais l'examen des commentaires de ces expressions toutes faites (qui souvent eux-mêmes s'apparentent au jeu... de mots) montre aussi que le détournement et la subversion, caractéristiques de l'usage littéraire des proverbes, affecte aussi ces formules, et que la tradition lexicographique brouille souvent les pistes qu'elle prétend éclairer.